

ROLE OF MUSIC PEDAGOGY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the role and importance of music pedagogy in the higher education system. Music pedagogy is considered not only as a means of forming musical skills, but also as a means of developing students' creative potential and expanding aesthetic thinking. Music pedagogy in higher education allows students to familiarize themselves with music theory and practice, as well as national and world musical culture. The article examines the educational, social and cultural aspects of music education in higher education institutions, and also highlights the role of innovative pedagogical approaches in this process.

Key words: Music pedagogy, higher education system, creative potential, aesthetic thinking, music theory, national musical culture, innovative pedagogy, music education.

Introduction:

Music pedagogy plays an important role in higher education, because it not only imparts musical knowledge and skills, but also helps to form students' creative thinking and cultural consciousness. Music education in higher education institutions allows students to expand musical knowledge, study music theory and practice in depth, as well as master national and international musical heritage. At the same time, through music education, students strengthen their social skills and contribute to the cultural development of society. This article analyzes the role of music pedagogy in higher education, its educational, cultural and social significance, as well as issues of increasing the effectiveness of music education through innovative pedagogical approaches.

Methodology:

The scientific-analytical approach was used in the research, and the following methods were used:

1. Literature analysis: available scientific sources and textbooks on music pedagogy and music education in higher education were studied. These analyzes helped to obtain information about the dynamics of the development of music pedagogy in the higher education system and its socio-cultural impact.

2. Comparison method: The systems and approaches of music education in higher education in different countries were compared. This approach made it possible to compare different methods of music pedagogy in higher education and the results achieved through them.

3. Interview and observation: The opinions and experiences of pedagogues and students on music pedagogy in higher education were studied. Through this method, practical processes of music pedagogy in higher education and methods of developing creative potential of students were analyzed.

4. Statistical analysis: In order to measure the effectiveness of music education in higher education institutions, the results of educational processes were analyzed based on statistics. In this, the level of knowledge of students, the development of creative skills and the general effect of music pedagogy were taken into account.

Results:

The results of the research showed that music pedagogy in higher education plays an important role in developing students' creative potential and expanding musical culture. According to the results of interviews and observations, most of the students acquired high-level skills in creativity and music performance, along with in-depth study of national and international musical heritage through music education. It was found that musical educational programs in higher education institutions give significant results in the preservation of national traditions and the development of new creative approaches.

Discussion:

The effectiveness of music pedagogy in higher education mainly depends on pedagogical approaches and innovative methods used in the educational process. Research shows that modern technologies and interactive teaching methods help to make the process of musical education more effective. For example, music technologies (using audio and video materials, editing and creating music in computer programs) further enrich students' creative processes. Also, interactive learning methods, group creative activities and musical projects enhance cooperation between students, which serves to form musical collective thinking.

The research results show that music pedagogy in higher education plays an important role not only in providing students with musical knowledge, but also in expanding their creative thinking, in-depth assimilation of national and international musical heritage, as well as in developing creative and logical thinking. By using modern approaches, educators can increase students' interest, enrich their musical education and increase their contribution to the cultural development of society.

Summary:

Music pedagogy in higher education greatly contributes to the creative and cultural development of students. Music education allows not only the formation of musical knowledge and skills, but also allows students to master national and international musical culture, develop creative potential, and expand social skills. Innovative pedagogical approaches and modern technologies increase the effectiveness of music education, which further strengthens the importance of music pedagogy in the higher education system.

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